

DEGRADATION AND COLLAPSE OF DYNAMIC SYSTEMS

Abstract – The management of reserve mechanisms and resources in biological, social, economic, energy and information systems are analyzed. The stages of degradation of such systems to the state of collapse are also described. Degradation involves the gradual decline in system performance and reliability. Dynamic Systems often operate under changing conditions, which can accelerate degradation. Collapse is the final stage where the system fails completely. Collapse can be sudden or progressive, depending on the system's resilience and the severity of the degradation. To predict and manage degradation, reliability models are used. These models help in understanding how systems degrade over time and in developing strategies to mitigate failure. Building resilience into systems can help them withstand degradation and avoid collapse.

Keywords – dynamic system, degradation, collapse, resilience.

1. THE MAIN COMPONENTS OF THE DYNAMIC SYSTEMS

A **system** is a set of interconnected modules or elements that work together as a whole to achieve a specific purpose or function.

Fig. 1. The main components of the dynamic system

The functional stability of the system is maintained through the management of its reserve mechanisms and resources, which are utilized to exert an appropriate influence on the system's structural organization and the processes occurring within it.

Under conditions of insufficient reserve mechanisms and resources for managing the structure and processes in the system, its ability to achieve a specific purpose or function is gradually or completely lost, that is, the system degrades to a state of collapse.

The management of reserve mechanisms and resources in biological, social, economic, energy and information systems are analyzed below. The stages of degradation of such systems to the state of collapse are also described.

2. MANAGEMENT OF RESERVE MECHANISMS AND RESOURCES IN SYSTEMS OF DIFFERENT NATURE

1.1. Management of reserve mechanisms and resources in biological systems are processes that ensure the stable functioning of biological systems and their ability to adapt to external and internal changes. Conservancy in biological systems refers to the ability of organisms to create reserve mechanisms or resources to sustain life in the face of stress or damage [1-3].

1. Homeostasis and reserve mechanisms

Homeostasis ensures the maintenance of a stable state in the body, but this requires reserves of energy, resources or functions. For example:

Energy reserves: Organisms build up glycogen stores in the liver or fat depots for energy use during starvation or exercise.

Water and salt reserve: The kidneys can regulate the excretion or retention of water and salts in the body to maintain balance during dehydration or excess fluid.

Thermoregulation: The body uses various mechanisms to maintain a stable body temperature, including heat reserves or cooling mechanisms.

2. Nervous system and reserve mechanisms

The nervous system coordinates the work of all body systems, but also has its own reserve mechanisms:

Backup neural connections: In the event of damage to certain neural pathways, the nervous system can activate alternative pathways to transmit signals.

Brain plasticity: The brain is able to adapt and create new connections between neurons in response to damage or learning.

3. Endocrine system and reservation

Hormonal regulation includes compensation mechanisms in case of violations:

Compensation of hormonal disturbances: If one hormonal pathway is disturbed, other systems can compensate for the deficiency. For example, with thyroid insufficiency, other glands can partially take over its functions.

Hormone reserve: In some cases, organisms have reserves of hormones that can be quickly mobilized in response to stress or body needs (for example, during stress there is a rapid release of adrenaline).

4. Immune system and reservation

The body's immune system also has backup mechanisms to provide protection:

Immune memory: After an infection, the body stores information about the pathogen and can react more quickly upon repeated contact.

Lymphocytes: The immune system has reserve lymphocytes that are activated when there is a threat to the body.

Antibody supply: After vaccination or acquired disease, antibodies remain in the body for a long time, ensuring a rapid response to familiar pathogens.

5. Cellular regulation and reserves

Cells have several reserve mechanisms to preserve their vital activity:

Energy storage: Cells can store energy in the form of ATP molecules or store fat for emergency use.

Reserve molecules: The body produces extra enzymes and proteins that can be used in times of stress or damage.

Autonomous reserves: Cells can switch to alternative metabolic pathways in the event of a lack of oxygen or nutrients (e.g., anaerobic metabolism).

6. Adaptation mechanisms and reserves in ecosystems

In ecosystems, backup mechanisms also exist to maintain resilience:

Biodiversity: The diversity of species in an ecosystem ensures its sustainability because different organisms perform similar functions. If one species disappears, others can partially compensate for its role.

Ecological niches: Different species have their own niches, but in case of changing conditions, some species can occupy new ecological niches and ensure the stability of the ecosystem.

7. Reservation at the genetic level

At the level of genetic regulation, there are also backup mechanisms:

Genetic plasticity: Organisms have genetic diversity that allows them to adapt to new environmental conditions and prevent population viability from declining.

Gene polymerization: Some organisms have multiple copies of genes, which allows them to compensate for mutations or loss of function in certain genes.

8. Molecular mechanisms of management and reservation

At the molecular level, organisms have several layers of management and redundancy:

Enzyme regulation: Having multiple enzymes for the same process provides a backup if one of the enzymes becomes inactive or not efficient enough.

Backup chaperone proteins: These proteins help maintain the proper structure of other proteins under stressful conditions, such as high temperatures or toxic environments.

Conclusion. Management and backup mechanisms in biological systems are extremely important for ensuring the viability of organisms and their ability to adapt. Conservation allows biological systems to conserve resources, provide compensation for environmental damage or change, and ensure the long-term functioning and sustainability of organisms and ecosystems.

1.2. Management mechanisms in social systems and reservation. Governance mechanisms in social systems determine the ways in which organizations, communities, or societies in general adapt to change, respond to challenges, and ensure their functioning. Effective governance is critical to maintaining the stability and development of social systems. Redundancy, in turn, is an important element in ensuring the reliability and stability of these systems [4-6].

The main management mechanisms in social systems:

1. State regulation

Government at the level of the state or local government determines the policies, rules and laws that regulate the activities of social systems. This may include social policies, economic regulations, environmental regulations, etc.

2. Management through education

Education is an important tool for forming values, norms of behavior and skills in society. Education systems help to ensure that the population is prepared for changes and challenges.

3. Social institutions

Institutions (family, religious organizations, public associations) perform the functions of social control, support and development of the community. They ensure social integration and play the role of mediators in conflict resolution.

4. Communication mechanisms

The interaction between the various participants in the social system is carried out through communication channels such as the media, social networks and public hearings. Effective communication ensures the exchange of information necessary for decision-making.

5. Adaptation mechanisms

Social systems must be able to adapt to changes in the external environment. This may involve modifying existing policies or creating new institutions to respond to current challenges.

6. Booking in social systems:

Redundancy in the context of social systems refers to the availability of additional resources, capabilities, or mechanisms that can be used to ensure system stability in the face of crises, challenges, or disruptions.

The main reserves in social systems:

7. Reserves of human resources

The presence of qualified personnel who can be involved in case of need helps the social system to respond quickly to challenges.

8. Financial reserves

The creation of financial reserves or funds helps to provide resources for the implementation of emergency measures in crisis situations.

9. Technological reserves

The use of modern technologies for monitoring, analysis and management of social processes provides the system with opportunities for quick response to changes.

10. Social reserves

Communities can develop support mechanisms such as volunteering or charitable organizations that can be activated in times of crisis.

Conclusion. Effective management and backup mechanisms are critical to maintaining the stability and resilience of social systems. They allow systems to adapt to change, respond to challenges and provide support to their members in difficult situations. Given the constant changes in the social, economic and ecological environment, it is important to constantly improve these mechanisms to ensure their effectiveness.

1.3. Management mechanisms in economic systems and reservation. Governance mechanisms in economic systems determine the ways in which resources are allocated, used and controlled to ensure the stability, development and efficiency of the economy. Reservation, in turn, is an important aspect in maintaining the reliability of economic systems, allowing them to adapt to changes and minimize risks [7-9].

The main management mechanisms in economic systems:

1. State regulation

The government determines economic policy, which includes tax, customs, financial and social policies, which regulate the behavior of economic agents. This may include legislation, regulations and government programs.

2. Market mechanisms

The market is the main mechanism through which the prices of goods and services are determined. Supply and demand interact, which ensures the distribution of resources and stimulates production.

3. Financial institutions

Banks and other financial institutions provide access to capital that allows businesses and individuals to finance investment and consumption. They also play an important role in controlling liquidity in the economy.

4. Planning and forecasting

Economic systems use planning and forecasting to determine resource needs, optimize production and distribution. This helps reduce uncertainty and risk.

5. Monitoring and control

The government and other organizations monitor economic indicators (inflation, unemployment, GDP) to control the state of the economy. This allows timely detection of problems and response to them.

The main reserves in economic systems:

6. Reservation in economic systems:

Redundancy in economic systems refers to the availability of additional resources, stocks or mechanisms that can be used to ensure the stability and resilience of the economy in the face of instability, crises or unforeseen circumstances.

7. Financial reserves

Governments and central banks create reserves (for example, gold and foreign reserves) to ensure the stability of the national currency and support the economy in times of crisis.

8. Reserves of goods

The presence of strategic reserves (oil, food, raw materials) allows countries to respond to external shocks and ensure economic security.

9. Manpower reservation

The development of programs for retraining and improving the qualifications of labor resources helps to reduce the negative impact on the labor market during economic changes.

10. Insurance and risk management

The use of insurance mechanisms helps businesses and households protect themselves from financial risks associated with unforeseen events (fires, disasters, changes in legislation).

Conclusion. Effective management and backup mechanisms are key to maintaining the stability and development of economic systems. They allow countries and businesses to adapt to changes, manage risks and ensure efficient use of resources. In today's world, where economic conditions are constantly changing, it is important to introduce new mechanisms and improve existing ones to ensure the stability and development of economic systems.

1.4. Management mechanisms in energy systems and redundancy. Energy systems are complex infrastructural complexes that ensure the production, transmission and distribution of energy. Effective management of these systems is necessary to ensure their stable operation, adapt to changes in demand, and respond to unforeseen events. Redundancy in power systems plays a key role in increasing their reliability and resistance to failures [10-13].

The main control mechanisms in energy systems:

1. Operational management and monitoring

This mechanism involves constant monitoring of the state of energy networks and generation. The use of automated systems allows timely response to changes in load or emergency situations.

2. Distributed management

In modern energy systems, distributed energy sources are widely used, in particular, renewable sources (solar, wind energy). This requires decentralized management mechanisms to ensure the integration and balancing of these sources in the overall system.

3. Demand planning and forecasting

Planning energy production based on demand forecasts helps avoid energy overloads and shortages. For this, mathematical models and analytical tools are used, which take into account seasonal fluctuations and trends in energy consumption.

4. Management of production and consumption

The introduction of "smart grid" technologies allows dynamically regulating not only production, but also energy consumption. For example, with the help of dynamic tariffs or automation in households and enterprises.

5. State regulation and energy policy

Governments regulate the energy sector through licensing, tariff setting, emission quotas and incentive programs for the development of renewable energy sources. This also includes monitoring compliance with safety and environmental standards.

The main reserves in energy systems:

6. Redundancy in energy systems:

Redundancy is an important element of the reliability of the energy system, which allows maintaining the stability of the energy supply in case of emergency situations, peak loads or failures in the operation of individual elements of the system.

7. Reserve energy sources

Reserve sources include both traditional (thermal, hydroelectric power plants) and alternative sources (energy accumulators, hybrid systems). In the event of failure of the main generators, backup sources can be quickly activated to cover the deficit.

8. Strategic reserves of energy carriers

The presence of strategic fuel reserves (coal, oil, natural gas) allows to ensure the stability of energy supply during crisis situations, such as supply interruptions or geopolitical conflicts.

9. Network bandwidth reserves

Bandwidth reserves are used to prevent overloads in the power grid. This allows for stable energy supply even with high peak loads or failure of individual sections of the network.

10. Emergency reservation

Includes duplication of critical components of power systems (power lines, transformers) and emergency shutdown of individual segments to prevent the spread of accidents to larger parts of the system.

11. Frequency and voltage regulation reserves

In power systems, it is important to maintain a stable frequency and voltage. For this, reserves of automatic regulators are used, which adjust the power of generators in real time.

Conclusion. Control and redundancy mechanisms in power systems are key to ensuring stable and trouble-free operation of these systems. Management allows for optimization of energy production, transmission and distribution, while redundancy creates an additional level of security that protects the system against accidents and interruptions. The effective integration of these mechanisms is becoming increasingly important in view of global changes in energy, in particular the development of renewable energy sources and the decentralization of energy networks.

1.5. Management mechanisms in information systems and reservation. Information systems are complex complexes that provide collection, storage, processing and transmission of data. Management of these systems is critical to ensure uninterrupted operations, security and data protection. Redundancy, in turn, helps ensure business continuity and minimize losses in the event of failures or attacks [14-16].

The main management mechanisms in information systems:

1. Data management

Includes the processes of organization, storage, processing and analysis of data to ensure their availability and correctness. It can be the management of databases, data warehouses and analytical systems.

2. Access and security management

Information systems must establish control over access to data and resources. This is achieved through authentication, authorization and data encryption. An important element is the role-based access control (RBAC) system.

3. Process management

Includes automation and coordination of business processes performed by the information system. This allows for consistent and efficient execution of tasks, minimizing manual interventions and errors.

4. Monitoring and auditing

Continuous monitoring of system performance, including network health, service performance, data availability, and security. An audit helps identify potential threats, deficiencies in system operation, and ensure compliance with legal regulations.

5. Incident and Business Continuity Management

Incident management mechanisms allow a quick response to failures or attacks in the information system. Business continuity plans are developed to minimize downtime and recover from unforeseen situations.

The main reserves in energy systems:

6. Reservation in information systems:

Redundancy ensures fault tolerance and security of the information system, which allows you to avoid the loss of data and functionality in the event of technical failures, cyber attacks or human errors.

7. Data backup

One of the key data protection mechanisms. Regular backups allow you to restore lost information in the event of a failure. Copies can be stored locally or in cloud services.

8. Fault-tolerant servers and cloud platforms

To ensure uninterrupted operation, fault-tolerant servers with duplicated components (power supplies, hard drives) are used. Cloud platforms also provide a high level of reliability due to distributed resources.

9. Reservation of network connections

Includes redundant communication channels and routers that ensure uninterrupted operation even in the event of failure of the main network equipment or connections.

10. Virtualization and containerization

Virtualization allows systems to be duplicated or moved to other physical servers without interruption. Containerization, particularly with Docker or Kubernetes, provides flexible redundancy and scalability.

11. Load balancing

The use of load balancing systems provides an even distribution of traffic or computing tasks among several servers or infrastructure elements, which prevents overload and failures.

12. Backup software and updates

Providing backup versions of the software and controlling the implementation of updates allows you to avoid failures as a result of erroneous updates or cyber-attacks on the system.

Conclusion. Management and redundancy mechanisms are critical to ensuring the reliable operation of information systems, especially in the face of modern threats such as cyber attacks and technical failures. Management allows you to maintain efficient system operation, control access to data and respond to incidents, while redundancy minimizes the risks of information loss and downtime.

3. DYNAMIC SYSTEMS DEGRADATION AND COLLAPSE

3.1. BIOLOGICAL SYSTEM

Degradation of a biological system is a gradual deterioration of the functioning of an organism or ecosystem under the influence of internal or external factors. It is characterized by the loss of biological functions, a decrease in resistance to stress and the inability to restore the previous state.

The collapse of a biological system is the final stage of degradation, when the system can no longer maintain its basic functions and disintegrates or undergoes a drastic change. Collapse leads to the loss of system structure, its functionality and, in ecosystems, can cause the disappearance of species and the destruction of ecosystem balance.

Stages of biological system degradation:

1. Initial stage:

At the initial stage, the system can maintain functionality, but minor disturbances in its work begin to appear, for example, a decrease in productivity or an increase in sensitivity to stress.

2. Progressive degradation:

Gradual increase of negative effects from external or internal factors. The functions of the system are increasingly disturbed, and it loses the ability to regenerate or adapt.

3. Approaching collapse:

At this stage, the system is no longer able to perform its main functions. Negative processes become irreversible, and restoration of system functions becomes impossible without external intervention.

4. Collapse:

The last stage, when the system collapses. This can manifest as the death of an organism, the extinction of a species, or the complete destruction of an ecosystem.

3.2. SOCIAL SYSTEM

Degradation of the social system is a process of gradual deterioration of the functioning of social institutions, norms and interactions between people in society. It manifests itself through a decrease in social cohesion, trust between citizens and the efficiency of state institutions. Degradation can occur under the influence of internal and external factors, such as economic crisis, political instability or environmental disasters.

The collapse of the social system is a more radical and drastic process when the social system loses its ability to function normally, which leads to massive social upheavals, chaos, the destruction of social order and the disruption of the basic functions of the state and society.

Stages of degradation of the social system:

1. Initial violations:

At this stage, signs of ineffectiveness of state institutions, growing inequality and social tension appear. Society is still functioning, but crises of confidence in the government and other institutions are beginning.

2. Deepening of the crisis:

Internal conflicts and social contradictions are intensifying. You can see the increase in economic inequality, the rise in crime, the decline in living standards and mass protests.

3. Instability and decline:

Social institutions become unable to maintain order and provide basic needs of citizens. This can lead to destabilization, weakening of state power and outbreaks of violence.

4. Collapse:

The social system is completely destroyed: institutions lose their effectiveness, chaos is observed, social control is lost, mass riots or even civil wars are possible.

3.3. ECONOMIC SYSTEM

Degradation of the economic system is a process of gradual deterioration of the functioning of the economy, which is manifested in a decrease in growth rates, a drop in productivity, deepening of inequality, unemployment, and an increase in poverty. Economic degradation is often accompanied by crises in various sectors of the economy, financial instability and lack of investment in development.

The collapse of the economic system is a sharper and deeper deterioration of the economic condition of a country or region, when the main economic mechanisms fail. The collapse leads to mass bankruptcy of enterprises, a sharp drop in the incomes of the population, hyperinflation, a crisis in the banking system and a decrease in the state's ability to fulfill its obligations.

Stages of degradation of the economic system:

1. Initial degradation:

Declining economic growth, falling investment and increasing unemployment. At this stage, the first signs of inflation or budget deficit can be observed.

2. Progressive degradation:

Aggravation of economic problems: a decline in production, an increase in the debt burden, a shortage of goods, and an increase in social inequality. At this stage, it becomes more difficult to provide the basic economic needs of the population.

3. Economic crisis:

A sharp drop in economic indicators, bankruptcies of enterprises, an increase in unemployment, a drop in the standard of living. The economy is becoming unstable and needs immediate measures to avoid collapse.

4. Collapse of the economic system:

Complete collapse of economic infrastructure, loss of control over financial institutions, hyperinflation, mass unemployment and shortage of goods. The state loses the ability to perform its social and economic functions.

3.4. ENERGY SYSTEM

Degradation of the energy system is a gradual deterioration of the functioning of the energy infrastructure, which leads to a decrease in the efficiency of energy production, distribution and consumption. This process can be accompanied by disruptions in the work of energy enterprises, wear and tear of equipment, insufficient investments in modernization and an increase in the

frequency of accidents. Degradation can seriously affect the stability of energy supply and economic development of the region.

The collapse of the energy system is a sudden and abrupt shutdown of a significant part of the energy infrastructure, which leads to massive power outages, stopping production processes and disrupting the life of the population. Collapse is often the result of systemic problems that have accumulated over time and can be caused by technical, natural or human factors.

Stages of energy system degradation:

1. Initial degradation:

In the initial stages, there may be minor disruptions in the operation of the energy infrastructure, an increase in the frequency of accidents and a reduction in the amount of investment in maintenance.

2. Progressive degradation:

At this stage, the problems become systemic: more frequent accidents, problems with energy supply in remote regions, rising costs for repairs and maintenance of old infrastructure.

3. Energy crisis:

There are massive power outages, a shortage of capacity to meet the energy needs of the population and industry. The number of accidents is increasing, the efficiency of energy production and transportation is decreasing.

4. Energy system collapse:

Collapse can occur as a result of large-scale technical accidents, natural disasters or military operations. It leads to the termination of energy supply to large regions, the shutdown of industrial enterprises and vital infrastructure facilities.

3.5. INFORMATION SYSTEM

Information system degradation is a process of gradual reduction of its functionality, efficiency and reliability. Degradation is manifested in a decrease in the speed of data processing, more frequent errors in work, a decrease in security and resistance of the system to external threats. Degradation can occur due to wear and tear of technical resources, outdated software, or improper system management.

The collapse of an information system is a critical moment when the system completely loses its ability to perform its functions. Collapse is accompanied by failure of key components, loss of data, inability to process information or access it.

Stages of information system degradation:

1. Initial degradation:

Slow system performance, more frequent crashes or delays due to technical issues or outdated software. At this stage, the system is still functional, but its reliability and performance are gradually decreasing.

2. Progressive degradation:

The system begins to fail more often, serious problems with access to information or its processing appear. The number of errors in the software increases, and users begin to experience significant inconvenience in working with the system.

3. Information crisis:

There are mass failures in the work of key components of the system, which leads to interruptions in the work of enterprises or institutions that depend on this information system. Without immediate intervention, the system may fail completely.

4. Collapse of the information system:

Complete system failure due to technical or software problems, cyber attacks or catastrophic events. Loss of the ability to access data, process information and maintain communication between system elements.

4. CONCLUSION.

Dynamic systems degradation and collapse refer to the process by which complex systems deteriorate over time and eventually fail. This can happen due to various factors such as wear and tear, environmental conditions, and operational stresses.

Degradation involves the gradual decline in system performance and reliability. It can be caused by factors like aging components, material fatigue, and external environmental conditions.

Dynamic Systems often operate under changing conditions, which can accelerate degradation. These dynamic environments include variations in temperature, humidity, load conditions, and other external factors.

Collapse is the final stage where the system fails completely. Collapse can be sudden or progressive, depending on the system's resilience and the severity of the degradation.

To predict and manage degradation, reliability models are used. These models help in understanding how systems degrade over time and in developing strategies to mitigate failure.

Building resilience into systems can help them withstand degradation and avoid collapse. This involves designing systems to be flexible and robust against various stressors.

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